

Study of the use of wallpaper to mitigate radon exhalation from building materials in indoor spaces

B. Ruvira^{*}, B. García-Fayos, B. García-Gimeno, J.M. Arnal, G. Verdú

Institute for Industrial, Radiophysical and Environmental Safety (ISIRYM), Universitat Politècnica de València, Camino de Vera s/n, Valencia, 46022, Spain

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ABSTRACT

Radon gas is known to exhalate from the ground and can enter and accumulate inside buildings. Many countries set radon limit concentrations and propose mitigation techniques applied in the outdoors to prevent radon from entering buildings. However, radon can also exhalate from building materials, e.g. cement, bricks, marble or tiles, contributing high concentrations indoors. Space ventilation is the most used technique to reduce the indoor radon concentration to safe limits, but sometimes, it is not enough. In these cases, it is necessary to apply alternative techniques. This work exposes a prevention technique to reduce radon concentration in indoor spaces that come from building materials or from the subsoil diffusing through basement walls, based on the use of wallpapers. The use of wallpapers is a common decorative technique in homes and buildings, which is compatible with interior finishes and is simple to apply, easily accessible, commercially available and inexpensive. Different commercial wallpapers were selected with a cellulosic and polymeric base and vinylic, cellulosic, latex or non-woven coating material. Configurations of single and double layers of wallpaper and a triple configuration by adding an intermediate layer of aluminium film have been tested. Tests to determine the reduction of radon concentration were performed, and diffusion coefficient and diffusion length were calculated following an adaptation of ISO/TS 11665–13 standard. Radon reduction of 90%, low-medium radon resistance and a diffusion coefficient around 10^{-11} m²/s were reached for single-layer configuration, and up to 98% of radon reduction, medium radon resistance and diffusion coefficient of 10^{-12} m²/s with double-layer configuration for dense non-porous base wallpapers with vinylic and non-woven coatings. Adding an aluminium foil intermediate in the double configuration improves the results of all wallpapers tested regarding radon reduction concentration, radon resistance, diffusion length and diffusion coefficient. Moreover, for the dense non-porous base made of non-woven fabric with a vinyl coating layer wallpaper, the diffusion length is shorter than the thickness of the sample in this configuration so the amount of penetrating radon will be reduced by the decay of radon in the wallpaper. Therefore, most radon would disintegrate along the sample and the concentration in the interior space would be lower. These results open a new alternative to protect indoor spaces from radon that access through walls or building materials based on a simple, easy and low-cost technique.

1. Introduction

Since radon was identified as a carcinogen by the World Health Organisation in 2009, many countries have adopted legislation to reduce the risk from radon exposure, either by setting limit concentrations or by proposing mitigation techniques to be used. The main objective of these measures is to protect people from inhaling radon from various sources (World Health Organization, 2009).

For example, in Spain, the Technical Building Code indicates that in new buildings radon barriers must be installed between the ground and

the foundations, and these barriers must have a diffusion coefficient of less than 10^{-11} m²/s and a thickness of at least 2 mm (Spanish Ministry for Transport Mobility and the Urban Agenda, 2019). Commercial radon barriers currently used are made of multilayer materials, mainly polymer and aluminium (Jiránek et al., 2008; Jiránek and Kotrbatá, 2011). Table 1 shows diffusion coefficient results for different radon barriers studied by other authors as an example.

However, although less important than the contribution from the soil, there is another potential source of radon, namely building materials. Some studies have measured radon exhalation from different

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail address: bearuqui@upv.es (B. Ruvira).

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Table 1
Radon diffusion coefficient of different materials.

Material	Thickness (mm)	Radon diffusion coefficient (m ² /s)	Reference
PVC	6.00	(8.62 ± 1.32)·10 ⁻¹³	Kumar et al. (2023)
Polyurethane (PU)	2.14 ± 0.20	(1.86 ± 0.60)·10 ⁻¹¹	Tejado-Ramos et al. (2024)
LDPE	1.00	(6.47 ± 0.17)·10 ⁻¹²	Papp and Cosma (2015)
PE-Al-foam-Al-PE	0.19 (foam not included)	(1.50 ± 0.10)·10 ⁻¹¹	Chen et al. (2009)
PP		6.4·10 ⁻¹²	Jiránek and Kotrbatá (2011)
Parafilm M (wax and polymers)	0.13	(3.20 ± 0.60)·10 ⁻¹⁰	Poncela et al. (2005)
Modified bitumen	1.00	(1.9–2.1)·10 ⁻¹¹	Gaskin et al. (2021)
Bisphenol A		(5.40 ± 0.12)·10 ⁻¹⁵	Pressyanov et al. (2011)

building materials and they found that some of them could be an important contributor to indoor radon activity. For example, granite could have an exhalation above 900 mBq/m²h (Keller et al., 2001; Shoqwara et al., 2013; Yousef et al., 2015), marble of 646.35 mBq/m²h (Shoqwara et al., 2013) and stone could exhale 413.35 mBq/m²h (Yousef et al., 2015). Other materials, like phosphogypsum, which is used to manufacture building materials such as cement or bricks (Saadaoui et al., 2017), have a radon exhalation of 6.70 mBq/m²h (24120 mBq/m²h) (Keller et al., 2001). Table 2 shows radon exhalation for different building materials.

Usually, good building ventilation is enough to reduce radon concentration in indoor spaces. However, in the last decades a greater concern for the environment and sustainability has led to the development of intelligent, more comfortable and energy-efficient buildings (Buckman et al., 2014). Strategies such as sealing windows and doors, and thermal insulation of walls, floors and roofs make buildings more energy-efficient (Buckman et al., 2014) but also airtight (Pampuri et al., 2018). If mechanical ventilation is not designed and operated properly (incorrect adjustment, wrong operating mode, poor maintenance shutdown or high recirculation rates (Arvela et al., 2014; Jeong and Cho, 2023)) high indoor radon concentrations can be achieved.

On the other hand, in the domestic environment, where ventilation is usually natural, external climatic conditions have a direct influence on ventilation rates (Gandolfo et al., 2017; Lugg and Probert, 1997), so that in areas with high radon concentrations in the soil, indoor radon concentrations above 300 Bq/m³ can be reached, the limit set by Directive 59 Euratom (Council of the European Union, 2013).

In cases where ventilation is not sufficient to reduce the concentration of radon in the interior space, coming from the ground or from the construction materials, it is necessary to apply new strategies. Several studies have investigated the use of different types of paints to assess their effectiveness in reducing radon concentration in indoor spaces (Al-Janabi et al., 2013; Gou and Wang, 1998), and Gao et al. (2008) has even patented a coating specifically created to slow down the radon entry. This work proposes the application of wallpapers as a simple and

Table 2
Radon exhalation from different building materials (Keller et al., 2001; Shoqwara et al., 2013; Yousef et al., 2015).

Building material	E _{Rn} (mBq/m ² h)	Building material	E _{Rn} (mBq/m ² h)
Concrete	1080	Natural gypsum	103.94
Black cement	258.28	Phosphogypsum	24120
Brick	163.70	Granite	1089.25
Gravel	150.05	Ceramic	347.74
Sand	317.71	Marble	438.79
Stone	413.35	Porcelain	246.14

low-cost solution, which will act as a barrier to radon in building materials and as an extra barrier to radon entering through cracks in the walls into closed spaces. Wallpapers are commercially available, simple to apply, compatible with building materials. They are composed of multilayered cellulosic and polymeric materials, which other authors have proven to function as radon barriers (Jiránek and Kotrbatá, 2011). Since the composition of the wallpaper is similar to that found in commercial radon barriers, i.e. polymeric materials, in this work, it has been studied the potential of the wallpapers as radon barriers for indoor spaces.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Samples

Four commercial wallpapers were selected for the test. The wallpaper samples have a similar grammage, between 170 and 180 g/m², provided by the manufacturer, and a thickness between 176 and 471 μm, measured with a micrometre (model 3006 from Baxlo Precision, with a 10 μm accuracy). Three of the samples have a non-woven base with a polymeric surface finish, while the fourth has a cellulose base and cellulose surface finish. A detailed description and a photograph of each sample are shown in Table 3.

A characterisation of the profile of the samples was carried out with a field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM), model ULTRA 55 from Zeiss and Oxford Instruments, and with the magnifying lens, model MZ APO from Leica Microsystems, which are in the Electron Microscopy Service of the UPV. The samples were tested with a single-layer configuration, a double-layer configuration (bonding two layers of the material with wallpaper glue), and a triple-layer configuration (wallpaper layer-aluminium-wallpaper layer all bonded with wallpaper glue).

2.2. Experimental set-up

The experimental set-up has been designed according to the guidelines of ISO/TS 11665–13 Standard, with a previously tested modification (Ruvira et al., 2022a). The radon accumulation chambers are made of stainless steel AISI 316L, with a volume of 0.801 L and a test area of 78.5 cm². The radon source, a sealed pitchblende stone with an activity of 1.469 kBq, is introduced into the source chamber and the wallpaper sample is placed between the two containers, which are sealed by O-rings and screws. The wallpaper base always faces the source chamber, so that radon passes first through the base and then through the surface finish before reaching the receiving chamber. The radon is extracted from the chambers and passed through a desiccant unit to keep the relative humidity below 10% to the RAD7 continuous detectors (from DurrIDGE), where the radon concentration is recorded at the same time for both containers every half hour for 48 h. The radon is returned to the chambers to maintain a closed loop. The average temperature inside the laboratory during the test was 22.91 ± 0.59 °C.

A leakage test was performed and the leakage rate was calculated, obtaining a value of 8.9·10⁻⁷ s⁻¹. As this value is less than half of the

Table 3
Materials tested description.

Material	Thickness (μm)	Composition (Base – Surface finish)	Grammage (g/m ²)
Wallpaper 1 (W1)	471.25 ± 8.35	Non-woven – Vinyl	170
Wallpaper 2 (W2)	332.50 ± 11.65	Non-woven – Non-woven	170
Wallpaper 3 (W3)	300.00 ± 42.09	Cellulose – Cellulose	180
Wallpaper 4 (W4)	176.25 ± 5.18	Non-woven – Latex	180

radon decay constant, the ISO/TS 11665:13 Standard determines that leakage could be negligible. More information about the methodology and calculation of the leakage rate can be found in (Ruvira et al., 2022a).

2.3. Calculation method

Each sample has been tested twice, so the results have been calculated with the mean of the experimental values. First, the mean concentrations of both chambers are calculated for the last 24 h of the test; this is used to calculate the reduction in radon concentration:

$$\text{Reduction}(\%) = \frac{C_{SC} - C_{RC}}{C_{SC}} \cdot 100 \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

Where C_{SC} is the mean radon concentration in the source chamber for the last 24 h and C_{RC} is the mean radon concentration in the receiver chamber for the last 24 h.

Then, the experimental data of the receiving chamber for the last 24 h are fitted to a straight line and the slope value (p) is extracted to calculate the exhalation from the test material to the receiver chamber (E_1):

$$E_1 (\text{Bq} / \text{m}^2 \text{s}) = p \cdot \frac{V}{S} \quad (\text{eq. 2})$$

Where V is the chamber volume (m^3) and S is the test area (m^2).

By entering this value of E_1 into the second expression (eq. (3)) for the exhalation, the value of the radon diffusion length (l) can be obtained by an iterative process:

$$E_2 (\text{Bq} / \text{m}^2 \text{s}) = \frac{2 \cdot C_{SC} \cdot l \cdot \lambda}{e^{(d/l)} - e^{(-d/l)}} \quad (\text{eq. 3})$$

Where λ is the radon decay constant ($2.1 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$) and d is the sample thickness (m).

Finally, the diffusion coefficient of the material can be obtained:

$$D (\text{m}^2 / \text{s}) = \lambda \cdot l^2 \quad (\text{eq. 4})$$

To also evaluate the suitability of the samples to act as a radon barrier, the radon resistance of the materials is calculated as (Jiránek and Svoboda, 2017):

$$R_{rn} (\text{s} / \text{m}) = \frac{\sinh d/l}{\lambda \cdot l} \quad (\text{eq.5})$$

The minimum radon resistance required for the barriers depends on the potential radon of the soil and the characteristics of the buildings. Table 4 presents the minimum radon resistances for different building conditions and radon soil concentration (Jiránek and Svoboda, 2017).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Single-layer wallpaper configuration

Fig. 1 presents the front view, the FESEM and the magnifying lens profiles obtained for a single-layer wallpaper configuration. The FESEM

Table 4
Minimum radon resistance of the barriers depending on radon soil concentration and building characteristics (Jiránek and Svoboda, 2017).

	Radon resistance (Ms/m)		
	Low radon area	Medium radon area	High radon area
Building with mechanical ventilation, active subsoil or air gap ventilation	7	25	50
Building with naturally ventilated habitable rooms in the basement	50	150	300

images have been obtained using a magnification between 70x and 170x, while the magnifying lens images have been obtained with a magnification of 63x for W1 and 80x for the rest of the samples. While W1 and W2 have a dense non-porous base made of non-woven fabric, W3 and W4 have a porous base made of cellulose or non-woven fibres, respectively. This configuration of the base materials has an impact on the behaviour of the wallpaper as a radon barrier due to the porous structure allowing more radon to pass through, as will be shown later in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 shows the evolution of the radon concentration in the source and receiver containers when 1 layer of each wallpaper is tested as a radon barrier. W1 and W2 reach a higher concentration in the source container (around 1 MBq/m³), while W3 and W4 have a concentration slightly above 500 kBq/m³. The concentrations recorded in the receiver container also vary, as for W1 and W2, they are below 100 kBq/m³, while for W3 and W4, they are around 500 kBq/m³.

Table 5 shows the average concentration over the last 24 h for both the source and receiver containers, the reduction in radon concentration achieved, the thickness of the tested material, the radon diffusion length and the calculated diffusion coefficient.

Comparing the results obtained for the four types of wallpaper, there are differences between them. Given that the grammage is practically the same, the differences may be due to the substrate material, surface finish and thickness.

W1 and W2 show the highest radon reduction percentages, with a value above 90% in both cases, and radon resistances, being between 11 and 28 Ms/m, which would make them suitable only for buildings with active mitigation measures in areas with low to medium radon concentrations in the soil (Jiránek and Svoboda, 2017). The diffusion coefficient ((1.65–2.99) · 10⁻¹¹ m²/s) and radon diffusion length (less than 3.78 mm) values are also very low in both cases. The diffusion coefficient obtained is close to the value indicated in the Spanish Technical Building Code for radon barriers in foundations (Spanish Ministry for Transport Mobility and the Urban Agenda, 2019); although there are no regulations for indoor radon barriers, this value could be used as a reference. Differences between both samples could be explained by the difference in the thickness, which shows that the higher the thickness, the higher the percentage of radon concentration reduction. Regarding the structure of the materials, both samples have a dense non-porous base made of non-woven fabric, which seems to give a structure that is more resistant to radon penetration. The surface finish has in both cases a microporous structure. No significant influence is observed on the result obtained from the material surface finish layer, which is made of non-woven fabric for W2 and vinyl for W1, and gives similar results.

On the other hand, W3 and W4 show radon reduction concentrations of 19.95 and 8.93% and radon resistances of 1 and 4 Ms/m, which means that they do not reach the minimum radon resistance for the most favourable scenario, that according to Table 4 is low radon area and buildings with mechanical ventilation. The diffusion coefficients are similar, being the highest for W4, as well as the radon diffusion length. These results may be due to the low thickness of the material (between 300 and 176 μm) but also to the nature of the constituent or coating materials. For W3, the base material is cellulose (in fibre form), and for W4, the base material is a porous, non-woven base. The fibre structure in both cases provides a lower resistance to the radon penetration, which is reflected in the low percentage of radon reduction achieved by these samples.

These results with a layer of wallpaper are promising, especially for W1 and W2, as the reductions in radon concentration of more than 90%, but also a medium radon resistance as a barrier that could prevent the accumulation of radon exhaled by the building materials in indoor spaces. Regarding the radon diffusion length, it is observed that for all wallpapers, values higher than the thickness of the material are obtained, which indicates that radon is able to pass through the wallpaper before disintegrating. For this reason, a double-layer configuration is tested made of a double wallpaper layer stuck with wallpaper glue.

Fig. 1. View of the surface finish and profile of the samples obtained with the FESEM and the magnifying lens for a single-layer configuration. The wallpaper base [1] would be glued to the wall while the surface finish [2] would be exposed to the indoor environment.

Fig. 2. Evolution of radon concentration in the source container (solid line) and the receiver container (dotted line) for 1 layer of each wallpaper sample.

3.2. Double layer configuration

Regarding the tests with two layers of wallpaper stuck, the front view and the electron microscope and magnifying lens profiles are presented in Fig. 3. These images have been obtained using the electron microscope at a magnification between 70x and 170x, while the magnifying lens was used with a magnification of 40x for W1 and 63x for the rest of

the samples. In all cases a uniform structure of the two glued wallpaper layers is observed.

When applying a second layer of wallpaper, it can be observed that the results improve compared to a single layer of wallpaper. The radon must first pass through the base (dense non-woven fabric or cellulose), then the surface finish, pass through the wallpaper glue, then the base again (dense non-woven fabric or cellulose) and finally the surface finish. The results, as will be seen later in Table 6, improve with the addition of the second layer of wallpaper.

Fig. 4 shows the evolution of radon concentration in the source and receiver chamber. As can be seen, the concentrations reached in the source chamber for W1 and W2 exceed 1 MBq/m³, while for W3 and W4, they hardly exceed 500 kBq/m³. Regarding the receiving chamber, W1 and W2 reach a concentration of around 50 kBq/m³, compared with concentrations of around 400 kBq/m³ for W3 and W4.

Table 6 shows the results obtained for 2 layers of the different wallpapers regarding the average concentration over the last 24 h for both the source and receiver containers, the reduction in radon concentration achieved, the thickness of the tested material, the radon diffusion length and the calculated diffusion coefficient.

For W1 and W2, radon concentration reductions of 99.07 and 98.62% are achieved, respectively, and the radon resistances have improved to values of 67 and 162 Ms/m, and could therefore be used in areas with low to medium radon content in the soil for naturally ventilated buildings according to (Jiránek and Svoboda, 2017). Radon diffusion length and diffusion coefficient have also improved, with lower values for these tests. The addition of the second layer has improved the reduction of radon concentration and decreased the radon diffusion length (although it is still greater than the thickness) and the

Table 5
Parameters obtained to calculate the radon diffusion coefficient of 1 layer of the different types of wallpaper.

Material	C _{SC} (kBq/m ³)	C _{RC} (kBq/m ³)	Radon concentration reduction (%)	Radon resistance (Ms/m)	d (μm)	l (mm)	D (m ² /s)
W1	958.39 ± 65.61	33.95 ± 8.24	96.46	28.74	471.25 ± 8.35	2.80	(1.65 ± 0.20)·10 ⁻¹¹
W2	842.75 ± 51.69	76.39 ± 18.74	90.94	11.11	332.50 ± 11.65	3.78	(2.99 ± 0.36)·10 ⁻¹¹
W3	501.27 ± 38.09	401.29 ± 36.29	19.95	3.45	300.00 ± 42.09	6.44	(8.72 ± 1.06)·10 ⁻¹¹
W4	502.73 ± 49.91	457.81 ± 47.04	8.93	1.40	176.25 ± 5.18	7.73	(1.25 ± 0.15)·10 ⁻¹⁰

Fig. 3. View of the surface finish and profile of the samples obtained with the FESEM and the magnifying lens for a double-layer configuration. The wallpaper base [1] of the first layer would be glued to the wall while the surface finish [2] of the second layer would be exposed to the indoor environment.

Fig. 4. Evolution of radon concentration in the source container (solid line) and the receiver container (dotted line) for 2 layers of each wallpaper sample.

diffusion coefficient (the latter by almost an order of magnitude).

As for W3, the addition of a second layer has slightly improved the reduction of radon concentration (from 19.95 to 27.07%) and the radon resistance (from 3 to 4 Ms/m), but still does not reach the minimum required radon resistance even for the most favourable conditions (low radon area with mechanical ventilation) specified in Table 4. However, it has increased the values of radon diffusion length and diffusion

coefficient (from 6.44 to 7.83 mm and from $(8.72 \pm 1.06) \cdot 10^{-11}$ to $(1.29 \pm 0.16) \cdot 10^{-10}$ m²/s). It is possible that the material type does not improve the length and diffusion coefficient, but the increase in thickness does influence the reduction in radon concentration and radon resistance.

About W4, the addition of a second layer of wallpaper makes little difference to the results obtained. The reduction in radon concentration improves by only 3% (from 8.93% for the single-layer test to 12.06% for the double-layer test) and the radon resistance increases from 1 to 3 Ms/m, although it still can not be used in any of the scenarios for radon resistance, according to Table 4. Regarding the radon diffusion length and the diffusion coefficient, the improvement is minimal as the diffusion length goes from 7.73 mm for 1 layer of paper to 7.35 mm for 2 layers, while the diffusion coefficient varies from $(1.25 \pm 0.15) \cdot 10^{-10}$ to $(1.13 \pm 0.14) \cdot 10^{-10}$ m²/s.

The addition of a second layer of wallpaper provides an extra layer of material that makes it more difficult for radon to pass through, both because of the increased thickness and the added material. Although this effect improves the results of the simple configuration in W3 and W4, it does not allow results comparable to those of W1 and W2 to be obtained, as they have a porous structure on the base that facilitates the diffusion of radon.

Therefore, a third test is proposed, in which an aluminium interlayer is added to the double-layer configuration to improve the results of samples W3 and W4.

3.3. Triple layer configuration

In these tests, a thin layer of aluminium (15 ± 7.56 μm) was added

Table 6
Parameters obtained to calculate the radon diffusion coefficient of 2 layers of the different types of wallpaper.

Material	C _{SC} (kBq/m ³)	C _{RC} (kBq/m ³)	Radon concentration reduction (%)	Radon resistance (Ms/m)	d (μm)	l (mm)	D (m ² /s)
W1	1027.78 ± 83.69	9.54 ± 1.57	99.07	162.62	927.50 ± 11.65	1.69	$(6.01 \pm 0.73) \cdot 10^{-12}$
W2	965.69 ± 71.81	13.28 ± 3.51	98.62	67.78	653.75 ± 14.08	2.16	$(9.76 \pm 1.18) \cdot 10^{-12}$
W3	472.69 ± 28.28	344.73 ± 28.23	27.07	4.18	537.50 ± 25.50	7.83	$(1.29 \pm 0.16) \cdot 10^{-10}$
W4	467.48 ± 39.32	411.09 ± 34.96	12.06	3.33	377.50 ± 4.63	7.35	$(1.13 \pm 0.14) \cdot 10^{-10}$

between the two layers of wallpaper and the adhesive was applied to bind them together. Therefore, radon passes first through the first wallpaper layer made of base (dense non-porous made of non-woven fabric or cellulose) and surface finish, the glue, then passes through the aluminium, the glue again and finally through the second wallpaper layer with the same structure.

Fig. 5 shows the front view and the images of the wallpaper samples obtained with the magnifying lens. The magnification used is 40x for W1, 63x for W2 and 50x for W3 and W4. All images show the triple configuration, consisting of layers of wallpaper (base material with the surface finish) with aluminium foil in the middle. As observed in the case of the double-layer configuration, the addition of a third layer increases the thickness of the material and the resistance of the material to radon penetration, especially for wallpapers with a dense non-porous base. The results will be shown afterwards in Table 7.

Fig. 6 shows the evolution of the radon concentration in the source and receiver containers when 2 layers of wallpaper and a thin aluminium foil are tested. W1, W2 and W4 reach a higher concentration in the source container (above 1 MBq/m³), while W3 has a concentration of around 850 kBq/m³. The concentrations recorded in the receiver container are, in all cases, below 10 kBq/m³; however, only W1 achieves a radon concentration in the receiver chamber around 1.5 kBq/m³.

Table 7 also shows the average concentration over the last 24 h for both the source and receiver containers, the reduction in radon concentration achieved, the thickness of the tested material, the radon diffusion length and the calculated diffusion coefficient for the different wallpapers with 2 layers and a thin aluminium foil. The same parameters for an aluminium foil sample are presented to compare the results (Ruvira et al., 2022b).

For W1, given that good results are already obtained with 1 and 2 layers, the addition of the intermediate aluminium foil does not considerably improve the radon reduction. However, the presence of aluminium reduces the radon diffusion length to 0.84 mm, below the thickness of the material, which means that most of the radon

Fig. 6. Evolution of radon concentration in the source container (solid line) and the receiver container (dotted line) for 2 layers of each wallpaper sample and a thin aluminium foil.

disintegrates before passing through the material. Regarding the diffusion coefficient, it decreases considerably from $(6.01 \pm 0.73) \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ for 2 layers of wallpaper to $(1.47 \pm 0.18) \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ when adding the aluminium foil. The radon resistance increases until a value of 845 Ms/m, which makes it suitable even for high radon areas and buildings with natural ventilation, according to Table 4.

With W2, good results are also obtained with 1 and 2 layers of wallpaper, but even so, adding the aluminium foil improves the results, especially the values of the radon diffusion length and the diffusion coefficient. The reduction of radon concentration improves slightly, but the radon resistance increases its value up to 208 Ms/m and could,

Fig. 5. View of the surface finish and profile of the samples obtained with the magnifying lens for a triple-layer configuration. The wallpaper base [1] of the first layer would be glued to the wall while the surface finish [2] of the second layer would be exposed to the indoor environment and the aluminium foil [3] would be between the two layers.

Table 7

Parameters obtained to calculate the radon diffusion coefficient of 2 layers of the different types of wallpaper and a thin aluminium foil.

Material	C _{Sc} (kBq/m ³)	C _{Rc} (kBq/m ³)	Radon concentration reduction (%)	Radon resistance (Ms/m)	d (μm)	l (mm)	D (m ² /s)
Aluminium	780.50 ± 45.18	10.33 ± 2.11	98.68	91.15	15.00 ± 7.56	0.28	(1.64 ± 0.20)·10 ⁻¹³
W1	1082.38 ± 101.51	1.06 ± 0.32	99.90	845.97	1003.75 ± 19.23	0.84	(1.47 ± 0.18)·10 ⁻¹²
W2	1079.15 ± 95.86	4.96 ± 1.28	99.54	208.88	655.00 ± 9.26	1.25	(3.29 ± 0.40)·10 ⁻¹²
W3	793.59 ± 44.55	6.60 ± 1.59	99.17	124.47	573.75 ± 15.98	1.50	(4.75 ± 0.58)·10 ⁻¹²
W4	1037.76 ± 89.74	5.26 ± 0.77	99.49	330.85	445.00 ± 21.38	0.82	(1.40 ± 0.17)·10 ⁻¹²

therefore, be used for buildings with mechanical ventilation in high radon areas and naturally ventilated buildings in areas with medium radon content in the soil, as it is shown in Table 4.

Concerning W3, the addition of the aluminium layer between the two layers of wallpaper considerably improves the results compared to one or two layers of wallpaper alone. The radon reduction and radon resistance, in this case, increase to 99.17% and 124 Ms/m, making it suitable for buildings with mechanical ventilation in high radon areas and buildings with natural ventilation in areas with low radon content, according to Table 4. The radon diffusion length is reduced to 1.50 mm. The value obtained for the diffusion coefficient is $(4.75 \pm 0.58) \cdot 10^{-12}$ m²/s, slightly higher than that of the other three materials but in the same order of magnitude; the addition of aluminium has managed to reduce it with respect to the tests without aluminium.

As for W4, placing a layer of aluminium between the layers of wallpaper greatly improves the results. The radon reduction is observed going from 8.93 to 10.77% for the single and double-layer tests to 99.49% when an aluminium layer is present and the radon resistance increasing up to 330 Ms/m, which makes it suitable to all building characteristics and radon areas as it has been discussed before. In addition, the radon diffusion length decreases considerably as a value of 0.816 mm is obtained, although it is still higher than the thickness and radon can pass through the material before disintegrating. For the diffusion coefficient, a value of $(1.40 \pm 0.17) \cdot 10^{-12}$ m²/s was obtained, two orders of magnitude lower than in the tests with the same material and comparable to the results obtained for the rest of the wallpapers.

Therefore, for samples W1 and W2, where the results were already very good, the addition of an intermediate aluminium layer in the configuration allows further improvement of the results, as another layer is added to the sample. However, the difference is noticeable in the case of W3 and W4, where the addition of the aluminium layer enables to obtain results comparable to those of W1 and W2, as the porous structure of the wallpaper is enhanced by the addition of another layer made of aluminium. Although aluminium is effective at preventing radon entry, it is fragile and thin and is difficult to apply to building materials. Inserting it between the wallpaper increases its mechanical strength and improves the results obtained with simple wallpaper configurations.

4. Conclusions

Current techniques to reduce indoor radon are focused on reducing the access of radon emanating from the ground or applying ventilation with fresh outdoor air to reduce the radon concentration. However, in cases where ventilation is not sufficient to reduce the concentration to safe limits or where the indoor radon concentration is worsened by the exhalation of radon from building materials, it is necessary to apply alternative techniques.

The use of wallpaper is a common decorative technique in homes and buildings, which is compatible with interior finishes and is simple to apply, easily accessible, commercially available and inexpensive. Their composition is usually cellulosic material or non-woven fabric combined with waterproof polymer-based finishes, which are materials used in commercial radon barriers that are designed to mitigate radon entry into buildings.

Wallpapers of dense non-porous base made of non-woven fabric (W1

and W2) in a single-layer configuration show a radon concentration reduction of over 90% and low-medium radon resistances and in a double-layer configuration, the radon concentration reduction is up to 98% and high radon resistances. In both cases, the diffusion coefficients are similar to the one required for standard outdoor radon barriers in the Spanish Technical Building Code, with a thickness of the material almost 5 times lower than commercial outdoors radon barriers. Best results is obtained for W1, which has a structure with a dense non-porous base made of non-woven fabric and a vinyl surface finish, reaching a 99.07% radon concentration reduction, diffusion length of 1.692 mm and diffusion coefficient of $(6.01 \pm 0.73) \cdot 10^{-12}$ m²/s with double-layer configuration.

Adding an aluminium foil interlayer in the double-layer configuration improves the radon concentration percentage, radon resistance, radon diffusion coefficient and radon diffusion length in all cases. The reduction of radon concentration in all cases is more than 99%, a high radon resistance up to 124 Ms/m, and the diffusion coefficient is in the range of $(1.40\text{--}4.75) \cdot 10^{-12}$ m²/s. Furthermore, in the case of the dense non-porous base made of non-woven fabric sample with vinyl surface finish (W1), radon resistance is up to 845 Ms/m and a radon diffusion length (0.84 mm) lower than the thickness of the sample (1.003 mm) is achieved, so that most radon would disintegrate along the sample and the concentration in the interior space would be lower.

These results open a new alternative to protect indoor spaces from radon that access through walls or building materials based on a simple, easy and low-cost technique.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

B. Ruvira: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **B. García-Fayos:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **B. García-Gimeno:** Investigation, Data curation. **J.M. Arnal:** Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **G. Verdú:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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